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INFORMATION AND ADVANTAGES OF TYPES OF COMMUNICATION SERVICES, THEIR CHARACTERISTICS AND UNIVERSAL COMMUNICATION SERVICES

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Abstract. *This article provides information on the types of communication services, their characteristics and differences from other types of services. It also presents the essence, composition and advantages of universal communication services.*

Keywords: *service, economic growth, communication services, telecommunications services, internet communication service.*

Communication services are a vital part of modern society, providing the foundation for information exchange in both personal and professional settings. These services encompass a wide range of solutions, including telecommunications, internet access, postal delivery, broadcasting and satellite systems. Communication services play a critical role in connecting people around the world, bridging gaps and enabling seamless collaboration. In today’s digital economy, these services have become even more sophisticated, incorporating advanced technologies such as 5G networks, the Internet of Things (IoT) and satellite-based internet. Their importance cannot be overstated, as they drive global connectivity, economic growth and innovation.

Communication services are systems and technologies that enable the exchange of information between individuals, organizations, or devices. They include tools such as telecommunications networks, internet providers, postal services, broadcasting channels, and satellite communications. These services facilitate the transmission of various formats of information - text, voice, images, and video - over wired or wireless channels. For example, telecommunications services enable voice communication via landlines and mobile phones, while internet services provide a platform for email, social media, and videoconferencing. Broadcasting services distribute information to large audiences through television, radio, and streaming platforms. Each of these services is essential to ensuring the global flow of information.

Communication services can be divided into different types based on the medium and purpose of communication. These include telecommunications, the Internet, postal services, broadcasting services, and satellite communications. Each type serves unique needs, from personal connectivity to mass media. Together, they provide seamless and efficient communication across different platforms and geographies. The following types of services can be included in the main types of communication services:

1. Telecommunication services are the foundation of modern communication. These services facilitate the transmission of voice and data over long distances using technologies such as fixed telephony, mobile networks, and VoIP (Voice over Internet Protocol). Rapid technological developments have transformed telecommunications

services.

2. Internet services are an integral part of the digital age. They provide users with access to the global Internet, which enables them to access information, social media, and cloud-based tools. Internet services are provided through a variety of technologies, including broadband, fiber optics, satellite Internet, and wireless networks.

3. Postal services are one of the earliest forms of organized communication. They involve the physical movement of letters, parcels, and other goods from one place to another. Despite the growth of digital communication, postal services remain relevant for legal, governmental, and personal needs.

4. Broadcasting services involve the delivery of audio and visual content to a mass audience. This includes traditional platforms such as radio and television, as well as digital platforms such as YouTube and Netflix.

5. Satellite communications services use satellites in Earth orbit to transmit data and signals over long distances. This technology is essential for areas where terrestrial networks are not available, such as remote islands or mountainous regions.

One of the most rapidly developing industries of our time is communication. The role of communication services cannot be overestimated - it is used in everyday life, in industry, in the military, and even in space. There are many types of communication, which are classified according to a number of characteristics: the method of information transmission, the type of equipment used, the scale of the network, the quality of coverage, areas of application, etc.

Communication services can also be classified according to other parameters:

- wired connection services (telephone, telegraph, Internet access);
- wireless connection services (cellular communication, mobile Internet).

Mobile communication is the most dynamically developing segment of the communication market. The market for cellular services has significantly increased its size over the past 15 years and continues to develop rapidly. The principle of operation of mobile communication is fundamentally different from traditional wired telephony, which allows subscribers to use new services.

To ensure stable reception of the signal, a coverage area is required. Unlike a wired telephone network, cellular operators use special equipment (base stations) installed throughout the region.

The stations are located at a certain distance from each other, forming a regular hexagon (cell) that provides the necessary coverage in a given area.

The types of communication services available to subscribers of cellular networks are:

- voice communication with a subscriber anywhere in the world;
- sending text messages (SMS);
- the ability to exchange small graphic data packages (MMS);
- wireless Internet access (GPRS, EDGE, 3G/4G technologies);
- the ability to make video calls;
- answering machine, call forwarding to another mobile device.

Due to the high competition in this segment and the constant struggle for new subscribers, communication services are constantly being improved, providing fast

access to the Internet and significantly facilitating communication between people regardless of distance.

The modern classification of communication services has the most obvious advantages. These are the high reputation of mobile and radio signal providers, environmental safety, innovative delivery tools, software quality and the required qualifications of employees.

Universal communication services are an important part of the modern telecommunications system. They represent a set of basic services available to all citizens of the country at affordable prices on their territory. These services play a significant role in ensuring equal access to information and communications for the population, regardless of their geographical location and socio-economic status.

The concept of universal telecommunications services arose in the middle of the 20th century, when many governments recognized the need to ensure universal access to telephone services. With the development of technology and the emergence of new types of communication, such as the Internet and mobile communications, the scope of universal services has been constantly expanding.

Today, universal communication services include not only traditional telephone communication, but also the use of high-speed Internet, postal services and other basic communication services. Their provision is regulated by special legislative acts and financed by the state.

The provision of universal communication services is an important task of the state, which contributes to social and economic development, improves the quality of life of citizens and helps to reduce the digital divide. In this regard, the concept of universal communication services, its implementation in different countries and the study of related problems and prospects are of great interest.

Thus, universal communication services are a set of basic telecommunication services that all citizens of the country should have access to at affordable prices, regardless of their geographical location and socio-economic status.

The main objectives of providing universal communication services are:

- Ensuring equal access to information and communications for all segments of the population.
- Promoting the socio-economic development of regions, including remote and sparsely populated areas.
- Supporting segments of the population in need of social protection, such as low-income citizens, people with disabilities, etc.

Thus, universal communication services are an important public policy tool aimed at ensuring equal access to communication technologies and services for all citizens of the country.

Thus, universal communication services play an important role in ensuring social equality, economic development and improving the quality of life of the population, especially in remote and underprivileged areas.

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